

Horizon 2020 Work programme

Food Security, Sustainable Agriculture and Forestry, Marine, Maritime and Inland Water Research and the Bioeconomy

Call

H2020-FNR-2020: Food and Natural Resources

Topic name

FNR-16-2020: ENZYMES FOR MORE ENVIRONMENT-FRIENDLY CONSUMER PRODUCTS

FuturEnzyme:

Technologies of the Future for Low-Cost Enzymes for Environment-Friendly Products

Final ID: 101000327

31/05/2025

INTER-CONSORTIA POLICY BRIEF

D8.21

2

MANUEL FERRER

CSIC

MARIE CURIE 2, 28049 CANTOBLANCO, MADRID, SPAIN

Document information sheet

Work package:	WP8, Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation
Authors:	CSIC (Manuel Ferrer, Patricia Molina), Cluster Enzymes for Greener Products
Document version:	1
Date:	31/05/2025
WP starting date:	01/06/2021
WP duration:	48 months
WP lead beneficiary:	ITB
WP participant(s):	CSIC as main contributor and all partners for providing feedback and suggestions for implementation
Deliv lead beneficiary:	CSIC
Dissemination Level:	Public
Type	Report
Due date (months)	48
Contact details:	Manuel Ferrer (mferrer@icp.csic.es), Patricia Molina (patricia.molina@icp.csic.es)

Summary

- 1. Scope of deliverable5
- 2. Cluster Policy Brief #1.....5
 - 2.1. Preparation of the document.....5
- 3. Cluster Policy Brief #2..... 10
 - 3.1. Preparation of the document..... 10
- 4. Conclusion 17

1. Scope of deliverable

This deliverable consists in a series of Policy Briefs through which to draft policy advices in which members of different consortia agreed. Precisely, the consortia involved are the components of the [Cluster Enzymes for Greener Products](#) (more info in D1.5). This material is available as open access via the project website and the ZENODO repository.

The Cluster set a Policy Working Group (PWG), led by REDINN (OXIPRO project's partner), that had its first meeting on 22 April 2022. The PWG met in 4 more occasions: 30 June 2022, 03 November 2022, 23 November 2023, and 18 April 2024.

2. Cluster Policy Brief #1

Although this activity was planned, and usually is carried out, at the end of the project, the Cluster decided to prepare a first Policy Brief (PB) sooner, following the advise of the Project Officers.

2.1. Preparation of the document

The Cluster prepared an initial policy brief with the objective of outline consumer concerns about the environment, the issues and challenges of specific industries in aligning with environmental, social and economic EC strategies, directives and policies, and how the 4 projects funded by the EC are addressing these challenges by developing novel enzyme technologies to make targeted consumer products greener, more sustainable and environmentally friendly.

The main text was prepared by REDINN using the outcomes of the meetings, and was revised, completed and approved by all the partners of the 4 projects forming the Cluster. The final document with the visual design was prepared as well by REDINN using the visual identity line chosen for the Cluster (colours and logo). It was released on February 2023.

It is entitled *Enzyme technologies for more sustainable consumer products*, and the structure is as follows:

- Key messages
- Consumer concerns about the environment
- The enzyme solution
- Supporting and informing policies for industry (sectors: textiles, detergents, cosmetics and personal care products, and nutraceuticals)
- Delivering results to inform policy
- Recommendations
- Logos, names, acronyms, and number of Grant Agreements of the projects

Printed copies of the project were made available at various in-person events and were also promoted through the project's social media channels. It was also sent to relevant policy actors of the countries of the projects' coordinators (e.g. Margarita Ruiz Sáiz-Aja, MITECO, Spain) as well as members of the EU.

The document, shown as it is in the following pages, is publicly available through [FuturEnzyme's Zenodo community](#) and the [project's website](#).

European Cluster Enzymes for Greener Products

Policy Brief | February 2023

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.7241303

Enzyme technologies for more sustainable consumer products

Key Messages

- Global greenhouse gas emissions (CO₂) are now at 38 Gt and may reach 60 Gt by 2050¹. Certain industry sectors significantly contribute to CO₂ emissions. Our success in reducing these emissions can be increased through the use of enzymatic solutions in targeted sectors.
- The integration of enzyme technologies in certain products, namely detergents, textiles, cosmetics, and nutraceuticals, has a proven potential to increase their sustainability. Greening textiles, detergents and cosmetics with enzymes can reduce the carbon demand by 42 million tons per year, according to recent estimates².
- A new EU Cluster - Enzymes for Greener Products - brings together the knowledge, expertise, and technological capacity of 56 research, industry, and innovation organisations across 17 countries to take on the challenge of applying enzymes to boost the development of greener products, fast-tracking them to market, and enhancing climate neutrality.

Enzymes are proteins that act as biological catalysts and help speed up chemical reactions

Consumer concerns about the environment

Currently, 63% of people across 17 countries say that climate change is “very serious” and are concerned about the state of the environment³ and particularly resource use and depletion: according to a European Commission survey⁴, 56% of EU consumers care about the environmental impact of goods and services. Eco-consumerism is on the rise, as are concerns about the impact of specific products such as household detergents, cosmetics, food, and clothes. European consumers are also willing to pay more for consumer products that are environmentally friendly.⁵

The enzyme solution

Growing environmental concerns have contributed to the rapid growth of the enzyme market as well as their use in various industrial and speciality applications. Enzymes can be ‘domesticated’ in such a way that they are now key actors in the circular economy with the potential to support sustainability, reduce environmental pollution, lower processing costs, and enhance product performance and functionality. Enzyme technologies have the potential to annually decrease CO₂ emissions by 1 to 2.5 billion tons, the carbon demand to synthesise artificial chemicals (currently 140,000) by 200 million tons, and chemical waste by 90 million tons.⁶ Hence, to meet this need for the production and supply of greener, more sustainable products, the Enzymes for Greener Products Cluster is leveraging the power of enzymes in the processing phases and in the formulation of consumer products, such as washing agents, textiles, personal care, cosmetics, and nutraceuticals.

Supporting and informing policies for industry

The results and findings from the Enzymes for Greener Products Cluster will provide new scientific insights to support and inform EC policy areas affecting specific industry sectors:

Textiles

Textiles have an annual worldwide production of 119 million tons⁷ but are manufactured using large chemical processes that emit 1291 million tons of CO₂, and bleaching processes that generate high biological and chemical oxygen demands. However, enzymes function at low temperatures, and being biodegradable there is no negative impact. Particularly important is the contribution of enzymes to the removal of residual spinning oils, acrylic acids, and dyes. Developing greener manufacturing practices, such as circular bio-bleaching processes, combined with efficient management of production and post-consumer textile waste generation, better recycling, and increasing textile lifespans will reduce the carbon footprint, add value, and make the industry more competitive. Enzymes applied in any of the steps in the textile production chain: fibre spinning; weaving and knitting; solvent cleaning; dyeing; washing; finishing; and cutting and sewing, can achieve an overall reduction of about 50-119 million tons of CO₂⁸

Detergents

Laundering detergents and processes create annual emissions exceeding 62 million tons of CO₂ and account for 25% of the carbon footprint of the clothing industry due to high levels of energy and water use.⁹ Owing to demands for hygienisation, further adverse effects are caused by detergents releasing antimicrobial chemical agents into our water systems, threatening aquatic life, and leading to antibiotic resistance. By enhancing the industry products and processes with enzyme technologies, we can enable laundering at lower washing temperatures with increased hygienisation and odour control. This reduces the need for frequent washing, leading to greater textile longevity. Life cycle assessments show that this effectively reduces the industry's carbon footprint.¹⁰ Moreover, using enzyme technologies to replace some of the required surfactants will help decrease CO₂ emissions by 5.9 to 15 million tons of CO₂ per year in the EU.¹¹

Cosmetics and personal care products

This sector is currently highly fossil-dependent due to the use of large volumes of petroleum-derived synthetic polymers. The production and extraction of active ingredients are notable sources of environmental impact, accounting for about 20% of the total. Recent estimates foresee a global production of about 10,000 tons of cosmetics and personal care products contributing to a total of 8-23 million tons CO₂. There is also the environmental cost when chemicals from these products reach our aquatic systems. The development of natural, biobased, and biodegradable products is therefore fundamental to competitive growth and reducing environmental impact. Enzyme technologies will replace the use of non-biodegradable polymers in the production of cosmetics. In sunscreens, enzymes will reduce the quantities of chemicals and pollutants being released in the environment while enhancing the UV properties. If eco-ingredients are produced with water- and low-temperature enzymatic processes, the industry's emissions could be lowered by 23%.¹²

Nutraceuticals

CO₂ emissions from nutraceutical production remain unquantified due to the industry's diversity and complexity. At the same time, there is considerable underutilisation of potential resources for nutraceutical products, such as anti-inflammatories, gut modulators, and nutritional supplements, which can be extracted from by-products from process side streams in other sectors, including the biomass and nutrient-rich waste from the fishing industry. Enzyme technologies can address both issues of underutilisation and waste. Two types of enzymes can broaden the scope of biobased ingredients and feedstocks for nutraceutical use: Xylans can be developed for digestive aids, anti-inflammatory and anti-microbial supplements, while oxidoreductases can improve the sensory qualities of proteins and omega 3. Enzymes can thus open new pathways in nutraceuticals, increasing the potential of supplements, and enabling product quality to be customized for targeted end users with specific requirements.

Delivering results to inform policy

The research output of the four projects closely aligns with key priorities of the EU, and the results and findings of the Cluster will support and inform EC policy areas that address the environment, climate change, the growth of the bioeconomy and sustainable development (Table 1).

Table 1 EC priorities and expected Enzyme Cluster research output that aligns with these

EU Bioeconomy Strategy 2018 ¹³	Enzyme technologies will drive future solutions for the bioeconomy transition and support the sustainability of biomass use as a resource. They can enable the exploitation of agriculture, forestry, and agro-processing residues which are otherwise used inefficiently and poorly valorised. Supporting greener industrial bioprocessing in this way will generate more sustainable bio-based products, enhance the bioeconomy, and contribute to the European Green Deal.
European Green Deal ¹⁴	Climate neutrality can be achieved using enzymes to reduce resource use and carbon footprints from current production processes. Novel products can be cascaded to interested parties to support long-term competitiveness. Training and information will be given to facilitate their uptake.
Circular Economy Action Plan ¹⁵	Enzyme technologies will provide new sustainable production processes and consumer products, thus increasing possibilities for circularisation of biomass. Wastewater generated from the use of novel biopolymers can be effectively treated by existing waste-water plants.
8th Environmental Action Program ¹⁶	Enzymes can help develop a toxic-free environment (air, water, soil), and protect, preserve, and restore biodiversity by boosting eco-innovation and its uptake. They can improve the environmental performance of products; boost demand for better resource-efficient products and production technologies and enable consumers to make informed choices.
Sustainable Consumption and Production Action Plan ¹⁷ Farm to Fork ¹⁸	The use of specific enzymes will facilitate the development of simple low-energy and lower-water consumption processes to convert biomass. The use of non-edible resources (xylans and oxidoreductases) in supplementing food and nutraceutical products will be demonstrated.
Sustainable Blue Economy ¹⁹	The novel technologies will support the protection of marine and aquatic resources by reducing the quantities of pollutants being released in the environment. They will also increase and transform value chains with new enzyme processes for transforming waste from the fishing industry.
EU Strategy on Adaptation to Climate Change ²⁰ Zero Pollution Action Plan ²¹	The reduction or removal of harsh processing conditions will render current methods more environmentally friendly. Products and processes are thus being created for zero environment toxicity, for example by developing biodegradable polymers, and reducing CO ₂ emissions as well as decreasing the consumption of chemicals, water, and energy in a number of cases.
EU Industrial Strategy ²²	Enzyme-enhanced processes and products will enable a paradigm shift to relevant bioprospecting supported by digitalisation. User-friendly algorithms for enzyme discovery underpins the digital transition of EU industry, and evolved enzymes and microbes can help generate more technically and economically feasible applications in diverse value chains in industrial biotechnology. The output will help the diversification of international partnerships and support the recovery of Europe's industry and economy by fast-tracking new market opportunities.
2030 Agenda and Sustainable Development Goals ²³	The development and deployment of enzyme technologies will support and influence the transformation from non-renewable to renewable products, strengthening EU competitiveness, and creating jobs in science, industry, and consumer sectors.

Recommendations

In taking up the challenge of harnessing enzymes to enhance the sustainability and environmental friendliness of the target products and bring them to the consumers, the four Enzyme Cluster projects recommend strong support from all sectors for the courses of action shown here:

EnXylaScope
Unleashing xylan's potential with enzymes to make it a key ingredient for a scope of bio-based consumer products

FuturEnzyme
Developing future technologies for low-cost enzymes for more sustainable and environmentally friendly consumer products

OXIPRO
Harnessing the power of novel oxidoreductases - diversifying enzymes for environment friendly consumer products

RadicalZ
Developing novel tools for faster enzyme discovery and engineering to support the creation of greener products

[Subscribe to our newsletter](#)

These projects have received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreements no's:

EnXylaScope 101000831
FuturEnzyme 101000327
OXIPRO 101000607
RadicalZ 101000560

3. Cluster Policy Brief #2

3.1. Preparation of the document

In this occasion, the main objective of this document was to respond to the proposal of the European Commission (EC) of an amendment to the REACH regulation to extend the use of the generic risk assessment (GRA) approach to respiratory sensitizers in consumer and professional uses. Enzymes, which are crucial for numerous industrial applications, are classified as respiratory sensitizers category 1, indicating they are considered among the most harmful chemicals. This policy brief intended to outline the significant concerns this amendment raises for the enzyme industry and argued for the safety and sustainability of enzyme technologies. The main claims are: to remove enzymes from the revision, create a new classification of enzymes, and to establish a high-level expert group to ensure that the revision is removed and act as a 'Watchdog'. The target of the PB#2 are Members of the European Parliament (MEPs) and EU Policymakers.

A survey was prepared by REDINN after discussion in an online meeting, and it was circulated amongst the 4 projects to fill it. With the outcomes, REDINN prepared the PB#2, which was revised and approved by the whole Cluster. It was released in April 2025, and advertised by the Cluster.

It is entitled *Integrating Enzyme Technologies into EU Policy Frameworks*, and the structure is as follows:

- Executive summary
- Key messages (summarizing in brief the most important aspects regarding enzymes, regulation, sustainability, policy and competitiveness)
- The role of enzyme technologies in driving UN sustainability goals and the EU 2030 Agenda
- Enzyme technologies as drivers of sustainable Innovation across key sectors (SSbD, REACH, alignment with European Green Deal, Circular Economy and Bioeconomy strategies, competitiveness in biomanufacturing, all with individualized recommendations)
- Policy recommendations for enzyme integration
- Conclusion
- References
- Logos, names, acronyms, and number of Grant Agreements of the projects

The document, shown as it is in the following pages, is publicly available through [FuturEnzyme's Zenodo community](#) and the [project's website](#) (linked to Zenodo).

Integrating Enzyme Technologies into EU Policy Frameworks

Executive Summary

Enzyme technologies are revolutionising industries by providing sustainable, efficient, and non-toxic alternatives to conventional chemical-based processes. These innovations directly align with the European Union's (EU) safety goals under the European Green Deal¹, Circular Economy Action Plan², Safe and Sustainable by Design framework (SSbD)³, and the Clean Industrial Deal⁴. However, regulatory inconsistencies - particularly within chemical classifications - pose significant barriers to the widespread adoption of enzyme-based solutions.

This policy brief draws insights from the FNR-16 projects (EnXylaScope, FuturEnzyme, OXIPRO, and RadicalZ⁵) and extensive stakeholder and consumer surveys, highlights the economic and environmental benefits of enzyme technologies, identifies regulatory obstacles, and provides clear policy recommendations to position enzymes as catalysts for Europe's green and digital transition.

At the same time, it emphasises the urgent need to adapt EU regulations to fully harness enzyme technologies as sustainable alternatives to conventional chemicals.

Enzymes are proteins that act as biological catalysts and help speed up chemical reactions

Key Messages

Enzyme technologies are essential enablers of sustainable innovation

They reduce reliance on hazardous chemicals, lower energy and water use, and support the circular economy across sectors like textiles, cosmetics, nutraceuticals, and detergents.

Current EU regulations, especially under REACH, create barriers to enzyme adoption

Automatic classification of enzymes as hazardous substances (e.g. respiratory sensitisers) does not reflect their actual use-case safety, limiting innovation and market access.

Safe and Sustainable by Design (SSbD) frameworks must better integrate sustainability

The SSbD process should consider not only safety but also environmental and socio-economic benefits of enzyme technologies, using balanced and holistic assessment approaches.

Policy support and regulatory streamlining are urgently needed

Fast-track approval pathways, harmonised regulations across member states, and reduced burdens for SMEs will help accelerate the uptake of enzyme-based innovations.

Investing in enzyme technologies will strengthen EU industrial competitiveness

Supporting enzyme innovation in biomanufacturing aligns with the EU Green Deal, Clean Industrial Deal, and Bioeconomy Strategy, positioning the EU as a global leader in sustainable industry.

The Role of Enzyme Technologies in Driving UN Sustainability Goals and the EU 2030 Agenda

Enzyme technologies serve as key enablers of Europe's transition to a more sustainable and competitive bioeconomy. These biocatalysts enable processes that lead to energy savings, eliminate harsh, toxic chemicals, and reinforce circular economy principles. Findings from the FNR-16 projects demonstrate enhanced sustainability from enzyme applications across multiple consumer products. Despite these environmental and industrial advantages, the current regulatory framework for chemicals, particularly REACH⁶ classifications, present challenges to investment, innovation, and large-scale deployment of enzyme-assisted solutions.

Sector	Enzyme Application	Environmental & Economic Benefits	Alignment with EU Policies
Nutraceuticals	Enzymatic hydrolysis of fish byproducts into high-value protein supplements.	Reduces food waste and CO ² emissions. Increases resource efficiency. Supports circular bioeconomy principles.	Circular Economy Action Plan: Supports waste valorisation. Farm to Fork Strategy: Strengthens sustainable food systems. Sustainable Blue Economy Strategy: Supporting sustainable fisheries and aquaculture.
	Production of new compounds with prebiotic activity from secondary waste streams	Reduces food waste and CO ² emissions. Increases resource efficiency. Supports circular bioeconomy principles	Circular Economy Action Plan: Supports waste valorisation. Farm to Fork Strategy: Strengthens sustainable food systems.
Textiles	Enzymatic bleaching and fibre processing replace toxic oxidants.	Reduces water pollution and chemical waste. Lowers energy consumption. Enhances fabric durability.	Circular Economy Action Plan: Promotes sustainable textile production. Chemicals Strategy for Sustainability ⁷ compliance: Reduces hazardous chemical use.
	Textile production from yarn involves multiple chemical-intensive steps requiring hot water for removal, which can be significantly reduced using enzymes.	Reduced water and energy consumption while allowing the removal of chemicals (such as silicones, spinning oils, etc.) without damaging the surface, enhancing durability.	Circular Economy Action Plan: Promotes sustainable textile production. EU Strategy for Sustainable and Circular Textiles: Lifecycle of textile products.
Personal care and cosmetics	Enzyme-based UV filters replace petro-derived alternatives in sunscreens.	Prevents marine pollution and coral bleaching. Reduces reliance on harmful petrochemicals. Enhances biodegradability.	EU Cosmetics Regulation: Ensures safe and sustainable ingredients. EU's Sustainable Blue Economy Strategy: Protects marine ecosystems.
	Enzyme-synthesised aroma and antioxidant compounds replace oil-derived alternatives and can be labelled as "natural" ingredients.	Reduces reliance on harmful petrochemicals. Enhances biodegradability and boosts regional development (e.g. by localized raw material production and upgrading). Sustainable production by using renewable resources.	EU Cosmetics Regulation: Ensures safe and sustainable ingredients
	Enzyme-based transformation of high-molecular-weight hyaluronic acid into "Mini HA" hydrolysates.	Enzymes break down hyaluronic acid into Mini HA of a defined size, optimising its anti-aging properties in cosmetic formulations. Reduces energy consumption.	EU Green Deal and Circular Economy Action Plan: Reducing energy consumption. EU Cosmetic Regulation: Ensuring a more sustainable, eco-friendly ingredients.
Liquid Detergents	Enzymes enable cold-wash detergents with biodegradable surfactants.	Reduces energy use and CO ² emissions. Minimises water pollution. Improves wastewater treatment efficiency.	Chemicals Strategy for Sustainability: Eliminates hazardous surfactants.
	Bio-based thickeners replace petrochemical-derived alternatives and are labelled as "natural" ingredients.	Use of secondary waste streams as feedstocks reduces reliance on harmful petrochemicals. Enhanced biodegradability of product and wastewater from their synthesis.	Circular Economy Action Plan: Waste and recycling Bioeconomy Action Plan.

Enzyme Technologies as Drivers of Sustainable Innovation across Key Sectors

A consumer survey revealed that while consumers value ecological solutions, they still prioritise product effectiveness, which can be effectively achieved through the application of enzyme technologies. Moreover, responses highlight enzyme technologies that enhance industrial efficiency, environmental protection, and product safety, reinforcing EU sustainability priorities.

Enzymes Align with Safe and Sustainable by Design (SSbD) Principles

The SSbD framework provides a structured approach to developing chemicals, materials and processes that are both safe and sustainable. Survey results confirm that enzymes align with several of the SSbD design guiding principles:⁹

SSbD1: Improving material efficiency by enhancing resource valorisation through the direct use of crude effluents from which enzymes can generate value selectively.

SSbD2: By replacing chemical agents in detergent formulations, contributing to minimizing hazardous chemicals.

SSbD3: Minimising energy use in industrial processes by operating under milder conditions.

SSbD4: Use renewable resources as raw materials for enzymatic transformations.

SSbD5: Reducing hazardous emissions in marine and terrestrial ecosystems.

SSbD6: Reduce exposure to hazardous chemical feedstocks, reagents and solvents by enabling the use for milder, less toxic alternatives.

SSbD7: By producing molecules that degrade into harmless components that do not pose any risk to the environment/humans, and by designing recycling strategies for wastewater.

SSbD8: Enzymes enable sustainability across the entire product lifecycle, from raw material use and transformation into sustainable products to end-of-life recycling.

Of the five steps in the assessment phase, SSbD assessments prioritise hazard classification, safety, and health aspects (steps 1-3).

This emphasis may create a bias, potentially leading to the exclusion of enzyme innovations despite their environmental sustainability and socio-economic benefits (steps 4-5).

Recommendations:

Ensure SSbD methodologies balance safety with sustainability.

Practise SSbD in the upcoming Horizon Europe work programme and consult enzyme-experienced stakeholders to adapt and improve methodologies as experience and knowledge become available.

Introduce standardised social and economic assessments to ensure a holistic sustainability evaluation.

Consider a matrix-based structure with multi-harmonised criteria decision analysis rather than the hierarchical approach currently undertaken.

Regulatory Barriers Under REACH Must Be Addressed

Survey findings highlight industry-wide concerns over the current automatic classification of enzymes as respiratory sensitisers (Category 1) under REACH, regardless of use case or exposure risk. This blanket classification of enzymes as 'substances of concern'⁹ threatens to limit market access for safe and beneficial enzyme-based products.

Recommendations:

Exempt enzymes from Category 1 Respiratory Sensitisers when used in low-risk, encapsulated, or controlled applications.

Ensure that historical safe use is considered in risk assessments.

Apply a case-by-case risk assessment instead of one-size-fits-all hazard classifications to ensure balanced regulation.

Ensure case-by-case optimisation of enzyme formulations by prioritising liquid, granulated, or immobilised advanced forms over fine powders, following SSbD principles.

Enzyme Technologies Support the European Green Deal, Circular Economy and Bioeconomy Strategies

Enzymes technologies are crucial enablers of the European Green Deal, Circular Economy and Bioeconomy strategies by reducing chemical use and waste, valorising industrial by-products and producing new molecules, and improving resource efficiency.

The FNR-16 projects demonstrate enzyme applications that directly support:

European Green Deal: The enzymatic production of advanced ingredients in consumer products enables the reduction of wastewater and energy consumption during both production and use phases, leading to lower Greenhouse Gas (GHG) emissions.

Farm to Fork Strategy: Enzymatic processes extract bioactives from fish waste and forestry by-products, reducing food system losses and improving nutraceutical production.

Zero Pollution Action Plan: Enzymatic detergents, containing less chemicals and requiring a lower dosage per wash, reduce water contamination and enable milder, less environmentally harmful wastewater treatments.

Chemicals Strategy for Sustainability: Boosting the innovation capacity for the production of safe and sustainable bioactive molecules. The enzyme-based production of advanced ingredients, especially those that cannot be obtained through conventional methods, enables high-functional cosmetic formulations (Cosmetic Strategy).

Industrial Strategy: Boosting methodologies that enable the transition to a green and digital economy.

Textile Strategy: Enzyme-based bleaching and cleaning eliminate or facilitate the removal of toxic chemicals from yarn while reducing water and energy consumption. Additionally, enzyme-based solutions support the recycling of textiles, making the process more sustainable.

Recommendations:

Integrate enzyme innovation at all TRLs into sustainable EU Bioeconomy and Circular Economy funding programs.

Facilitate regulatory approvals for enzyme-driven valorisation, renewable and recycling technologies.

Enhancing European Competitiveness in Biomanufacturing

The Clean Industrial Deal and EU Industrial Strategy 2030 prioritize sustainable manufacturing and technological leadership. Enzyme technologies can drive the shift towards biomanufacturing, reducing the EU's reliance on fossil-based chemical processes and its dependence on imports.

Recommendations:

Provide financial incentives for enzyme-based biomanufacturing under new funding calls.

Streamline regulatory pathways to accelerate enzyme commercialisation.

Support the establishment of EU-wide enzyme innovation hubs and clusters to foster research collaboration.

Policy Recommendations for Enzyme Integration

To align enzyme technologies with the EU's sustainability and industrial strategies, policymakers should consider the following actions:

- Update REACH to reflect enzyme-specific properties.
- Establish dedicated assessment criteria that consider enzyme biodegradability and low toxicity.
- Differentiate (biochemical) enzymes from conventional chemical substances in classification and risk evaluation.
- Harmonise enzyme regulations across EU member states.
- Encourage mutual recognition of enzyme safety assessments across regulatory bodies.
- Streamline approval processes for sustainable biotechnologies.
- Introduce fast-track approval pathways for enzyme innovations that meet EU sustainability objectives.
- Reduce administrative burdens for SMEs and start-ups bringing enzyme-based solutions to market.
- Promote enzyme awareness and market uptake.
- Develop public awareness campaigns on the safety and benefits of enzymes and enzyme-based products.
- Support industrial transition programs to encourage private-sector adoption of enzyme technologies.

By implementing these policy reforms, the EU can unlock the full potential of enzyme technologies, driving innovation while achieving its ambitious climate and industrial objectives.

Conclusion

Aligned with past evidence, the FNR-16 projects highlight the transformative potential of enzyme technologies in achieving Europe's sustainability and industrial goals. However, to fully leverage these benefits, policy measures are urgently needed to ensure that enzymes are not disproportionately restricted under existing regulatory frameworks.

By implementing risk-balanced, science-driven regulations and incentivising enzyme innovation, the EU can lead the global shift towards sustainable industrial biotechnology while enhancing economic competitiveness.

Enzyme technologies offer a win-win solution for Europe's environmental and economic goals by reducing industrial carbon footprints, improving efficiency, and fostering sustainable manufacturing. However, to fully leverage their potential, EU policymakers must address regulatory barriers that hinder their adoption. By modernising regulations, harmonising policies, and supporting market integration, enzymes can become central drivers of Europe's green and circular economy.

This policy brief urges the European Commission, national governments, and industry leaders to take decisive action in integrating enzyme technologies within the EU policy framework, ensuring their role in shaping the sustainable industries of tomorrow.

1. <https://ec.europa.eu/green-deal>
2. <https://ec.europa.eu/circular-economy-action-plan>
3. <https://ec.europa.eu/ssbd-framework>
4. https://commission.europa.eu/topics/eu-competitiveness/clean-industrial-deal_en
5. <https://www.enxylascope.eu/>; <https://www.futureenzyme.eu/>; <https://www.oxipro.eu/>; <https://radicalz.eu/>
6. <https://echa.europa.eu/regulations/reach>
7. <https://echa.europa.eu/hot-topics/chemicals-strategy-for-sustainability>
8. https://www.parc-ssbd.eu/wp-content/uploads/2023/10/JRC131878_01.pdf; <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cogsc.2023.100876>
9. https://www.europabio.org/wp-content/uploads/2022/09/2022_08_L_PP_AMFEP-EuropaBio-Position-on-Taxonomy.pdf
10. <https://www.enzymetechnicalassociation.org/enzymes/safe-handling-enzymes/#:~:text=In%20fact%2C%20rennet%20has%20been,%2C%20starch%2C%20and%20baking%20industries;>
<https://www.efsa.europa.eu/en/efsajournal/pub/7464>; <https://amfep.org/about-enzymes/safety/consumers-safety/>

European Cluster - Enzymes for Greener Products

EnXylaScope

Unleashing xylan's potential with enzymes to make it a key ingredient for a scope of bio-based consumer products
<https://www.enxylascope.eu/>

FuturEnzyme

Developing future technologies for low-cost enzymes for more sustainable and environmentally friendly consumer products
<https://www.futureenzyme.eu/>

OXIPRO

Harnessing the power of novel oxidoreductases - diversifying enzymes for environment friendly consumer products
<https://www.oxipro.eu/>

RadicalZ

Developing novel tools for faster enzyme discovery and engineering to support the creation of greener products
<https://radicalz.eu/>

These projects have received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreements no's:

EnXylaScope	101000831
FuturEnzyme	101000327
OXIPRO	101000607
RadicalZ	101000560

4. Conclusion

Since it was stated that 1 inter-consortia policy brief would be produced, and the Cluster has produced 2, we consider the deliverables achieved.